
The difference between the equivalence principle in the gravitational field and the inertial frame

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abstract The equivalence principle is the cornerstone of the general theory of relativity, and about Newton's equivalence principle: the experimental verification that the inertial mass and the gravitational mass are equal has been very accurate.

This paper mainly discusses the strict distinction between the gravitational field and the inertial frame in the ideal gravitational field, in order to clarify the application scope of the equivalence principle. This paper proves that the effect of gravity on an object is actually a real "force" that is evenly distributed throughout the object, and the object in the process of free fall in the gravitational field is strictly different from the inertial system in free space.

At the same time, there is also a strict distinction between an object stationary in a gravitational field and an object undergoing uniform acceleration. This paper proves that the relativistic velocity transformation effect required by the inertial frame will occur in different directions in an object undergoing uniform acceleration. This paper once again proves the relative independence of inertial systems in space, and the relativistic effect is actually a transformation rule between different inertial systems based on the conservation of energy and momentum.

Keywords : equivalence principle, gravitational field, acceleration field, inertial frame

1 Introduction

Einstein used the famous elevator thought experiment to illustrate the principle of equivalence: light in a gravitational field and in a uniform acceleration field, the motion of light seen by the observer is parabola. At the same time, the elevator in free fall is equivalent to the inertial frame of uniform motion in the cosmic vacuum ^[1].

In addition, Einstein also used the redshift effect of photons in the gravitational field to explain the clock slowing effect in the gravitational field ^[1]. We have already explained in two other articles that the gravitational redshift actually originates entirely from the conservation of energy under gravitational action and should not be interpreted as a time delay effect ^{[2][3]}.

In order to more strictly prove the essential difference between the gravitational field and the inertial frame, and more strictly answer the real reason for the

"movement slowing effect" in different reference frames of relative motion, we will strictly demonstrate this in this article, to prove that there is no "clock slowing effect" and "" length contraction effect, but a relativistic effect based on the *conservation of energy, the conservation of momentum and the relative independence of the inertial system space* .

2 The difference between objects in free fall in the gravitational field and uniform motion in the inertial system

Thesis 1: Even in a perfectly ideal gravitational field, the physical laws of a free-falling object are fundamentally different from the inertial frame of uniform motion. The effect of gravity on matter is a real force, but gravity acts on every part of matter, so we cannot perceive the "conduction effect" of the force in the inertial system.

As shown in Figure 1 below:

Fig 1 Free fall motion of ideal gravitational field

First, we assume that there is a perfectly ideal gravitational field (where the gravitational lines are parallel and of equal magnitude), and the gravitational acceleration is constant g . A black box A is in free fall in a gravitational field.

We assume that a photon of frequency is ω emitted from the upper point P_1 of the black box A to the lower P_2 point, and the upper and lower length of the black box is L . Then when a photon is received at the point below the box P_2 , we must be able to observe the Doppler blue-shift effect of the photon, as shown in Figure 2 below:

Fig 2 Doppler effect in ideal gravitational field

Assume that the object A emits and absorbs photons before and after the speed is v unchanged (does not affect the conclusion), The time for the photon to travel from P_1 to P_2 is $t = \frac{L}{c}$. Suppose the initial velocity of the object is $v (v \ll c)$, The height at which the object falls at time t is $h = vt = v \cdot \frac{L}{c}$, $L \gg vt$. (we ignore the effect of gravity on the velocity of black box A in time)

The distance that the photon travels in the gravitational field in time t is: $L + vt$, greater than the height h at which the object falls in the gravitational field (where $h = vt$). Since gravity does work, it means that the photon energy should increase from P_1 to P_2 : $W = FS = \frac{h\omega}{c^2} \cdot gL$. Therefore, the photon will produce a blue-shift effect at P_2 . And this is a property that the inertial frame of uniform motion does not possess.

Therefore, even in a very small local area, if we assume that we can define such a small area ^{[1][4]}, then our assumption is that we can do the corresponding physical experiments and measurements in such a small local area. Then we should also be able to measure the difference from the inertial frame in the gravitational field of a

free fall.

Conclusion: The inertial frame of an object doing free fall in a gravitational field and a uniform motion are different and can be strictly distinguished, and this difference can be distinguished by physical experiments in any gravitational field. In fact, what an object is subjected to in the gravitational field is the actual "force". The difference from the acceleration obtained by the force of the object in the acceleration system is that gravity acts on every part of the object, and this property is related to the force conduction in the inertial system. The effects and feelings are completely different .

The above experiments are also applicable to objects stationary in an ideal gravitational field and objects in uniform acceleration motion. We only need to throw the object into the air to make it fall freely, and repeat the above experiments to distinguish the gravitational field from the inertial frame.

At the same time, the above experiments are not only valid for photons, but also for general objects.

Therefore, we can answer the following two questions:

1) Newton's equivalence principle: gravitational mass and inertial mass are strictly equal ^[7], because there is no substantial difference between gravitational and inertial forces, and they are both real forces. For this, we have actually discussed in another article ^[3].

2) Einstein's weak equivalence principle and strong equivalence principle: Fundamental non-gravitational test physics is not affected, locally and at any point of spacetime, by the presence of a gravitational field. All test fundamental physics (including gravitational physics) is not affected, locally, by the presence of a gravitational field ^{[4][6]}. Through the above experiments, we have proved that the strong equivalence principle does not hold. If the Doppler frequency shift effect belongs to non-gravity experiments, it also proves that Einstein's weak equivalent distance does not hold.

2 The difference between an object at rest in a gravitational field and a uniform acceleration

Thesis 2: The force performance and physical phenomena of objects at rest in the gravitational field are also different from the physical phenomena in objects moving with uniform acceleration. Objects at rest in the gravitational field do not have the relativistic effects due to space independence, momentum conservation and energy conservation, but in the accelerating field, relativistic effects due to energy conservation and momentum conservation will occur.

We take the following thought experiment as an example to illustrate, also assuming that this is a uniform gravitational field, as mentioned above, the gravitational acceleration is g . Object A is at rest in a uniform gravitational field, the object B is accelerating at a uniform acceleration in the universe with a constant

acceleration g . Suppose that our observation system S is stationary relative to the initial states of A and B.

We assume that there are two identical devices on object A and object B respectively. There are two spheres in the device doing symmetrical and uniform circular motion on a circular orbit (for simplicity, we ignore the frictional force on the orbit), The static mass of each ball is m_0 , the speed of the circular motion of the ball is v , so their total momentum $P = 0$. The plane of circular motion of the sphere on object A is perpendicular to the direction of gravity, and the plane of circular motion of the sphere in object B is perpendicular to the acceleration direction g , and B starts to accelerate from a resting state. As shown in Figure 3 below:

Fig3 Difference between acceleration field and gravitational field

Then in the A reference frame or the B reference frame, the dynamic mass of each ball m_1 is:

$$m_1 = m_0 \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2}}$$

After the elapse of time t , we assume that the speed of the object B in the universe has reached v_1 , where $v_1 = gt$. At this time, looking at the circular motion of the

two small balls on the object B through the S system , the circular motion speed v will slow down; while the motion speed of the ball on A stationary in the gravitational field v will remain unchanged.

Prove:

We accelerate the ball on B in the vertical direction of its circular motion, which is equivalent to accelerating an object with a static mass of m_1 , assuming that the speed of B after acceleration is v_1 , so the dynamic mass m_2 of the ball after acceleration will become :

$$m_2 = m_1 \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v_1^2}} = m_0 \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2}} \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v_1^2}} \quad (1)$$

From the point of view of the S system, if the motion speed V of the object in circular motion remains unchanged (the direction of motion of V is perpendicular to the direction of acceleration g of the spacecraft B), then if the ball is released to let it fly freely, at this time, the moving speed of the ball is the combined speed of the horizontal speed and the vertical speed, and the combined speed is:

$$V = \sqrt{v^2 + v_1^2}$$

At this point we will observe a ball with a static mass of m_0 and a velocity of $\sqrt{v^2 + v_1^2}$, then its dynamic mass is:

$$m_0 \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - (v^2 + v_1^2)}} \quad (2)$$

We subtract formula (1) from formula (2) above to get:

$$m \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - (v^2 + v_1^2)}} - m \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2}} \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v_1^2}} > 0$$

Therefore, if the S system sees that the small ball moving in a circular motion on the object B does not change the speed v perpendicular to the acceleration direction, it will lead to the non-conservation of energy, and the energy of the ball will increase. This will violate the law of conservation of energy, therefore, the speed v of the ball on the spacecraft will definitely slow down in the view of the S system. (**Note that**

seeing here refers to if the ball entered the S-frame and was measured. The S-frame observer cannot determine the velocity of the ball without measuring it.)

We assume that after the spacecraft B accelerates to v_1 , the circular velocity of the sphere changes from V to v_2 . We can easily obtain the velocity of the sphere in the S system after acceleration by the following equation:

$$m \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - (v_2^2 + v_1^2)}} = m \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v^2}} \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{c^2 - v_1^2}}$$

Solve the equation to get:

$$v_2 = \pm \frac{v}{c} \sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2} \quad (3)$$

(Of course, v_2 it can actually be obtained directly from the relativistic velocity transformation formula, but through the above thought experiment, we can have a deeper understanding of the essence of the relativistic velocity transformation formula, which is actually the velocity transformation under the conservation of momentum and energy)

Several explanations for the above conclusion:

1) Special relativity explanation

According to the special theory of relativity, the inertial frame of relative motion has the effect of slowing down the clock. The relative motion speed of the S system and the B system is v_1 , then the time relationship between the two coordinate systems is:

$$\frac{dt_1}{dt} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2}}$$

After time transformation, we can obtain the transformation relationship of the above formula (3). However, we have proved in another paper that the hypothesis of slower time will encounter many problems in the experiment ^[5], and similar experiments can be deduced that the slower time leads to contradictions. We can have more designs.

2) Interpretation of relative spatial independence

From the perspective of the reference frame of spaceship B, the moving speed of the sphere v is constant. Assuming that its orbital radius is r , its motion period

$T = \frac{2\pi r}{v}$ is also constant, that is, the time remains constant.

In previous articles we have concluded that time is absolutely simultaneous from the perspective of both the B system and the ground S system ^[5], so how do we

explain this slowing effect ? In fact, as we proved in another paper, the relativistic transformation is just a transformation of the conservation of energy and momentum [2].

From the perspective of the B reference frame: the speed of the ball is v , its physical meaning is observed in the B reference frame, and the kinetic energy and momentum of the ball are measured by the speed v .

And after the acceleration of the spaceship B, relative to the S reference frame, the momentum and energy of the small ball in uniform circular motion on B is measured by the speed v_2 . This kind of speed transformation between different inertial systems is only a transformation rule to ensure energy conservation and momentum conservation under the premise that the inertial system space is relatively independent, and it does not mean "time becomes slower" or "length shrink".

Each independent inertial frame is a relatively independent system of conservation of momentum and energy, and constitutes a relatively independent space.

Therefore, in the S reference frame, we will not see the "clock slowing" and "length contraction" on the B reference frame. These speed transformation effects will only occur when the two reference frames are related because of "energy conservation" and "Conservation of momentum" is observed.

2.2 For the object A at rest in the gravitational field

Conversely, when we observe A stationary in the gravitational field, the speed of the ball in the ball device above it, after the elapse of time t , from the point of view of the S reference frame, we can't actually see any change in the velocity v of the ball, otherwise, there will be a dilemma of energy conservation.

Similarly, we assume that there are two identical spherical devices at different heights h_1 and h_2 ($h_1 > h_2$) on the earth's gravitational field, and their initial spherical motion speeds are both V , and their initial motion periods are both T . According to the conclusion of general relativity, it should be observed that the velocities of the two spherical devices will become different over time due to the effect of the clock slowing down, and the motion period of the ball at position h_1 will be slower than that of the ball at position h_2 movement cycle^[1].

But in fact, if we ignore the influence of uneven gravitational force and the friction force, there should be no difference in the motion periods of the two spherical devices T , otherwise the observer at any angle will encounter an energy-conserving predicament. Where does the lost ball kinetic energy of the slow ball device go?

3 Rediscussion on the relative independence of space

In another article we have discussed the relativistic aberration effect ^[2], as shown in Figure 4 below:

Fig 4 Relativistic aberration effect

And have the following conclusions:

$$\frac{\sin \theta}{\sin \theta_1} = \frac{\omega_1}{\omega} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{v}{c} \cos \theta\right)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\sin \theta}{\sin \theta_2} = \frac{\omega_2}{\omega} = \frac{\left(1 - \frac{v}{c} \cos \theta\right)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

This angular effect is also a relativistic effect, just as we cannot directly deduce "the clock is slowing down" from "relative speed is slowing down". Similarly, we cannot say that because of the Doppler effect, the angle of the photon observed by the observer changes, and the real position of the moving object A relative to the S system changes.

Therefore, we can draw the following conclusions:

The relativistic effect is not caused by the slowing down of time and the contraction of length, but is based on a physical law required by the inertial frame. The physical laws of any inertial system are the same, which means that any inertial system must obey its own law of conservation of energy and momentum, and its inertial system space must be relatively independent; however, due to the difference in relative motion speed between different inertial systems, different inertial When transforming energy conservation and momentum conservation between systems, the rules of relativistic transformation must be followed.

Therefore, the relativistic transformation formula is only a set of physical laws derived from the relative independence of the inertial system space and the observance of energy conservation and momentum conservation between different inertial systems.

4 Conclusion

Through theoretical analysis, we have actually proved the correctness of Newton's weak equivalence principle: the reason why gravitational mass and inertial mass are equal is that they are both subject to "force". Gravity is a real force, not a space-time bending effect.

At the same time, we have strictly proved the strict distinction between the gravitational field and the inertial system. Therefore, whether it is the weak equivalence principle of Einstein's theory of relativity or the strong equivalence principle of Einstein's general theory of relativity, we actually proved that it is not strictly equivalent effective.

Through a series of thought experiments, this paper once again proves that the relativistic effect is actually a transformation requirement for energy conservation and momentum conservation in different inertial frames based on the relative independence of inertial frame space. It's not a clock-slowness effect, nor a length-shrinking effect.

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